

Supplementary Material – Text S1

Protologues for new prokaryotic taxa

Etymology and description of the new taxa proposed under SeqCode.

Bifidobacteriaceae Stackebrandt et al. 1997 emend.

Family defined by phylogenomic analysis. Members form a monophyletic group that shows a relative evolutionary divergence (RED) similar to that of the neighboring families. Contains the genera *Ancillula* Strasser and Brune, *Aeriscardovia* Simpson et al. 2004, *Alloiscardovia* Huys et al. 2007, *Bifidobacterium* Orla-Jensen 1924, *Bombiscardovia* Killer et al. 2014, *Galliscardovia* Pechar et al. 2017, *Gardnerella* Greenwood and Pickett 1980, *Metiscardovia* Okamoto et al. 2007, *Neocardovia* García-Aljaro et al. 2015, *Nutricula* Kästle Silva and Brune, *Opitulatrix* Kästle Silva and Brune, *Pariscardovia* Jian and Dong 2002, *Pseudocardovia* Killer et al. 2014, *Scardovia* Jian and Dong 2002, and *Servula* Kästle Silva and Brune.

Ancillula gen. nov. Strasser and Brune

Etymology: An.cil'lu.la. L. fem. dim. n. *Ancillula*, a little female servant.

Synonym: "*Candidatus* *Ancillula*" Strasser et al. 2012 (not validly published)

Description: Genus defined by phylogenomic analysis of metagenome-assembled genomes and single-cell amplified genomes. Members of the genus form a monophyletic group that shows a relative evolutionary divergence (RED) similar to that of the neighboring genera. Members of this genus are *Ancillula trichonymphae* sp. nov. (Strasser and Brune), *Ancillula hodotermitis* sp. nov. (Kästle Silva and Brune), *Ancillula glyptotermitis* sp. nov. (Kästle Silva and Brune), *Ancillula kalotermitis* sp. nov. (Kästle Silva and Brune), *Ancillula prorhinotermitis* sp. nov. (Kästle Silva and Brune).

Type species: *Ancillula trichonymphae* sp. nov.

Ancillula trichonymphae sp. nov. Strasser and Brune

Etymology: tri.cho.nym'phae. N.L. gen. fem. n. *trichonymphae*, of *Trichonympha*, a genus of termite gut flagellates.

Synonym: "*Candidatus* *Ancillula trichonymphae*" Strasser et al. 2012 (not validly published)

Description: Short, slightly pleomorphic rods (approximately 1.2 mm in length and 0.3 mm in diameter) with a typical Gram-positive cell wall. Colonize the cytoplasm of a lineage of closely related flagellates (*Trichonympha* Cluster II) in the hindgut of termites. SSU rRNA genes form a cluster of host-specific phylotypes.

Type genome: ImTpAt1ST, GCA_000485475.1 (genome); JQ993633 (16S rRNA).

Additional genomes: GCA_031276145.1.

Ancillula hodotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: ho.do.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *hodotermitis*, of *Hodotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 34.5% and the estimated genome size is 1.51 Mbp.

Type genome: Hm464_bin179, GCA_031262545.1 (genome), OR396865 (16S rRNA).

Ancillula glyptotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: glyp.to.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *glyptotermitis*, of *Glyptotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 37.92% and the estimated genome size is 1.80 Mbp.

Type genome: Gsp477_bin129 from the lower termite *Glyptotermes*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031268675.1 (genome), OR396855 (16S rRNA).

Ancillula kalotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: ka.lo.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *kalotermitis*, of *Kalotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 49.22% and the estimated genome size is 1.07 Mbp.

Type genome: Kf353_bin77 from the lower termite *Kalotermes flavicollis*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031273495.1 (genome), OR396858 (16S rRNA).

Ancillula prorhinotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: pro.rhi.no.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *prorhinotermitis*, of *Prorhinotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 46.36% and the estimated genome size is 0.673 Mbp.

Type genome: Pc512_bin108 from the lower termite *Prorhinotermes canalifrons*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031280795.1 (genome), PP623112 (16S rRNA).

Opitulatrix gen. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: O.pi.tu.la'trix. N.L. fem. n. *Opitulatrix*, a female helper, maid.

Description: Genus defined by phylogenomic analysis of metagenome-assembled genomes. Members of the genus form a monophyletic group that shows a relative evolutionary divergence (RED) similar to that of the neighboring genera.

Type species: *Opitulatrix rosinitermitis* sp. nov.

Opitulatrix rosinitermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: roi.si.ni.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *rosinitermitis*, of *Rosinitermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises only metagenome-assembled genomes. The species includes all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 33.45% and the estimated genome size is 0.98 Mbp.

Type genome: Roe453_bin28 from the lower termite *Rosinitermes ebogoensis*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031288355.1 (genome); OR396864 (16S rRNA).

Additional genomes: GCA_031288055.1, GCA_031288095.1.

Opitulatrix cubana sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: cu.ba'na. N.L. fem. adj. cubana, of Cuba, Cuban, referring to the geographic origin of the host.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genomes. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 35.44% and the estimated genome size is 0.768 Mbp.

Type genome: Ncb351_bin81 from the lower termite *Neotermes cubanus*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031283665.1 (genome); OR396859 (16S rRNA).

Nutricula gen. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: Nu.tri'cu.la. L. fem. n. *nutricula*, a wet nurse

Description: Genus defined by phylogenomic analysis of metagenome-assembled genomes. The single genome shows a relative evolutionary divergence (RED) similar to that of the neighboring genera.

Type species: *Nutricula glyptotermitis* sp. nov.

Nutricula glyptotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: glyp.to.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *glyptotermitis*, of *Glyptotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 43.55% and the estimated genome size is 1.54 Mbp.

Type genome: Gx485_bin43 from the lower termite *Glyptotermes* sp.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031263495.1 (genome); OR396856 (16S rRNA).

Servula gen. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: Ser'vu.la. L. fem. dim. n. *servula*, a young servant girl

Description: Genus defined by phylogenomic analysis of metagenome-assembled genomes. The single genome shows a relative evolutionary divergence (RED) similar to that of the neighboring genera.

Type species: *Servula neotermitis* sp. nov.

Servula neotermitis sp. nov. Kästle Silva and Brune

Etymology: ne.o.ter'mi.tis. N.L. gen. n. *neotermitis*, of *Neotermes*, a genus of termites.

Description: The species comprises one metagenome-assembled genome. The species will include all bacteria with more than 95% average nucleotide identity (ANI) to the type genome. The GC content of the type genome is 42.03% and the estimated genome size is 1.1 Mbp.

Type genome: Nm470_bin85 from the lower termite *Neotermes meruensis*.

GenBank accession number: GCA_031281695.1 (genome); OR396861 (16S rRNA).